

**Accessible, reliable and affordable solar irrigation for
Europe and beyond**

Deliverable 2.13

**EAFRD Financial Instrument for
Photovoltaic Irrigation**

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Acronyms

CAP	Common Agrarian Policy
CPR	Common Provisions Regulation
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ESCO	Energy Service Company
FI	Financial Instrument
FRR	Fair Rate of Return
GHG	Green House Gasses
KEMT	Key Enabling Materials and Tools
kWh	Kilo-watt hour
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
MA	Managing Authority (of the RDP)
MW	Mega-watt
MWp	Mega-watt peak
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
PVI	Photovoltaic Irrigation
RDP	Rural Development Plan
SPV	Special Purpose Vehicle
TPO	Third Party Ownership
TWh	Thera-watt hour

Executive Summary

Most of the Mediterranean agriculture and food production rely on the output of more than 11 million ha of irrigated land. In order to achieve the required level of production, more than 60 billion of m³ of water are pumped each year from dwells, rivers and reservoirs to the fields. The process has a very significant economic and environmental cost, as more than 24 TWh of energy is consumed, and more than 4 million tons of CO₂ are released into the atmosphere. In order to mitigated the related negative impacts, a change in the energy model of irrigation is needed, as part of the overall policy goal of the CAP of fighting climate change.

The decarbonization of irrigation will require large investments in energy efficiency improvements and, in particular, in the introduction of several gigawatts of photovoltaic irrigation (PVI) systems. PVI systems consist in the integration of a photovoltaic generator and an irrigation infrastructure, allowing to supply all or most of the energy consumed by the pumps with renewable and clean solar energy in a reliable manner. The technology has evolved sufficiently as to present a suitable alternative for most irrigators. Nevertheless, PVI also requires high up-front investments and specialized operation and management procedures, often resulting in a cost of energy higher than that of incumbent, fossil-fuel based, alternatives. As a result, the competitiveness of PVI is not guaranteed, especially if the availability of affordable and long-term finance for the projects is limited.

This document presents a financial instrument (FI) specially designed to increase the competitiveness of PVI and to facilitate the introduction of quality standards in designing, building and operating the systems. The FI can be funded by the European Agrarian Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and be included by the Managing Authorities of the Rural Development Plans of the Common Agrarian Policies. It consists in guarantees to be provided by banks in order to improve the terms and conditions of loans used to fund PVI systems with the required level of technical, legal and financial quality. The result will have a direct impact on the cost of the energy produced by PVI, on the quality of the systems and on the participation of local SMEs in the related business opportunities.

The proposed EAFRD FI is part of the results of the project SolaQua. This document contains a detailed description of its operativity as well as a practical guide to support Managing Authorities and other stakeholders interested in supporting the decarbonization of irrigation. In this regard, the following sections describe the necessary actions that must be carried out in

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order to assess the suitability of the FI to a specific RDPs and indications to produce the necessary ex-ante assessment.

Introduction

SolaQua in a nutshell

Irrigated agriculture accounts for 33% of freshwater use in Europe (estimated at 60 billion m³/year), while in southern regions, it consumes up to 80%. To pump this water from wells, EU farmers consume more than 24 TWh every year, mainly from the grid but also a significant part (20%) from diesel generators (Martinho, 2016). Such an amount of energy causes greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions of more than 4 million tons of CO₂. In this context, combining the use of solar energy systems for irrigation and precision agriculture techniques represents the best alternative to conventional electric and diesel-based pumping systems (Lorenzo et al. 2018). As in many other sectors, photovoltaic (PV) technology can be integrated into existing irrigation infrastructures to supply the required energy while dramatically reducing GHG emissions. The resulting solution, known as PV irrigation (PVI), is increasingly being used to supply energy for small-sized farms or for larger farms in combination with conventional technologies that serve as backup.

However, the use of PV in medium and large sized installations was, until recently, only suitable if a back-up was available to supply 100% of the power with batteries or grid connections. This technical requirement is needed because critical parts of large irrigation infrastructures work at high pressure and are very sensitive to sudden changes in the power supply. Relatively small variations in PV power can easily cause serious damage to the irrigation infrastructure due to over voltages and water hammers, that reduce dramatically the lifetime of the electric and hydraulic systems, respectively. In order to prevent these problems, PVI had to add a set of batteries of equivalent size (up to 2 MWs) or a conventional power source that could instantly compensate any PV power fluctuation due to, for example, passing clouds. As a result of this intermittence and the related need for backup, PVI was not economically viable for the majority of irrigation infrastructures dominating the sector: the medium to large pumping systems.

The profitability of irrigated farming is extremely sensitive to the cost of electricity. As long as PVI systems rely on full scale backups it will not be possible to offer the solution at competitive cost. This problem has affected the attractiveness of PVI, increased its capital costs to uncompetitive levels and prevented large-scale uptake of the technology. However, a number of innovations that appear over the last few years, finally allows PVI systems of any scale to work fully independently of any back-up while guaranteeing the integrity of the infrastructure. These

solutions can integrate the hydraulic part, the PV generators and the frequency converters in order to guarantee that the pressure parameters are always within the infrastructure operational values, even in the case that the PV power experiences a sudden drop. By ensuring the compatibility of directly-connected PV with irrigation infrastructures of any size farmers can finally build large scale PVI systems at competitive cost even in places without suitable grid connections or in areas where the existing grid is saturated. Nevertheless, even if the possibilities offered by these innovations can considerably increase the competitiveness of medium to large scale PVI, its market uptake is being hampered by a number of non-technological barriers.

Nevertheless, many farmers still consider PVI as a risky investment due to its relative long payback time and perceived uncertainty over the actual performance of the system (Pombo 2022). Furthermore, the cost of the resulting energy in terms of Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) is often higher than incumbent alternatives such as diesel generation or connections to the electricity grid. In this regard, positive externalities of PVI such as CO₂ emissions avoidance or reduction of energy cost volatility are not reflected in LCOE.

The need to decarbonize EU's farming and to support clean energy investments in the sector has already identify by public authorities and included in the relevant policies and tools. Thus, the Common Agrarian Policy (CAP) and the Rural Development Plans (RDPS) established a number of goals, strategies, objectives and measures that are compatible with the support of PVI investments¹. Nevertheless, the specific characteristics of PVI indicates that tailored tools must be implemented to effectively support the adoption of PVI. These tools must address the barriers identified.

SolaQua is an initiative led by the Polytechnical University of Madrid aimed to facilitate the market uptake of PVI in Europe and beyond. The consortium of SolaQua, which represents more than 70% of European irrigators, includes all the relevant expertise and networking necessary to produce and disseminate the relevant information and solutions that are needed to unleash the potential of PVI. The members of SolaQua understand that, in order to fulfil the potential of PVI, it is necessary to overcome the existing barriers to its market uptake, including the lack of a dedicated CAP supporting tool. In order to fill this gap, SolaQua has organized a multidisciplinary

¹ The common agricultural policy (CAP) has three clear environmental goals, each of which are echoed in the [European Green Deal](#) and [Farm to Fork strategy](#): 1) tackling climate change; 2) protecting natural resources and 3) enhancing biodiversity.

working group that has been focused in producing an European Agrarian Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) financial instrument (FI) tailored to PVI. The result is one of the 7 **Key Enabling Materials and Tools (KEMT)** produced by SolAqua to support potential users in dealing with the technical, legal and economic aspects of planning, building and operating and supporting reliable and competitive PVI.

Purpose and scope

This document has been produced in order to support RDPs' Managing Authorities (MA) and other stakeholders to assess, design and implement a PVI-tailored EAFRD FI. EAFRD FIs can support investments in the agricultural sector by addressing financial needs that the market is not well suited to deal with on its own. This is often the case of modernization projects for farms which are fundamentally viable but lack access to the necessary finance because they do not meet the requisites of traditional lenders such as banks. Among other issues this situation can be caused because borrowers cannot provide sufficient guarantees (collateral) or fail to present a track record of performance which is necessary for the bank to assess the riskiness of the loan. As a result, access to loans is reduced, interest rates are increased and repayment periods shortened, negatively affecting the economic viability of modernization projects in the agrarian sector. PVI projects are particularly sensitive to the described problem, as they require high initial investments and long payback periods. In this regard EAFRDs FIs can be implemented to facilitate PVI projects access to suitable finance in the form of loans, guarantees or equity, and to facilitate to attract further finance to the decarbonization of the irrigation sector.

As one of the main objectives of EAFRD FIs is to leverage public and private investment into the agriculture sector, it is particularly desirable the existence of a common framework for PVI among the different RDPs at national and at European level. As investors normally have a national or even continental scope, the existence of common regulatory and supporting frameworks related to PVI will facilitate their interest in the asset class and the scalation of their related operations. This document aims at providing such common framework on the basis of cost-effectiveness in the use of public funds, positive impact at farmers' level, easiness of implementation and alignment with CAP objectives and regulations. The contents of the document are based on the knowledge and experience of the partners of SolAqua regarding the

technical, regulatory economic and commercial framework of PVI and in the common provision regulation (CPR) of EAFRD FI².

In order to serve as a practical guide for RDPs' MAs and other relevant stakeholders, **the document is structured following the sequence of actions that must be carried out to implement EAFRD FIs in the RDPs**. In this regard EU regulation established the need to produce a document, the ex-ante assessment, justifying the need of the FI and describing the details of its operation. The ex-ante assessment must be produced following a specific methodology (EC/EIB 2016) and receive the approval of EAFRD authorities before MAs can include the FI in the RDP.

Ex-ante assessments are complex and detailed documents that can consume significant resources from MAs to be produced, resources that are not always sufficiently available. Furthermore, PVIs have specific characteristics in terms of technical, economic and regulatory issues that must be taken into consideration when designing and implementing a tailored EAFRD FI. As a result, it is relevant to produce materials to support MAs interested in implementing EAFRD FIs suited to irrigators. In this regard, the consortium of SolAqua includes partners highly specialized in the different aspects related to PVI, agricultural finance and RDP managing. This multidisciplinary expertise has allowed to produce a EAFRD FI specifically designed to the needs of irrigators, investors and MAs. The FI is aimed to increase the attractiveness of PVI projects by reducing the cost of the resulting energy to competitive levels with incumbent alternatives but also by introducing quality standards to protect farmers and guarantees to reduce the riskiness of the investments.

The present document contains a detailed description of the FI, which can be complemented with other KEMT of the SolAqua project³. MAs can use it to support the production of their own ex-ante assessment and the implementation of the FI. Nevertheless, this document is not an official guidance and its use or the implementation of the proposed FI remains entirely under the responsibility of the MAs.

² Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and laying down general provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1083/2006.

³ Related materials can be found at <https://sol-aqua.eu/documents/>

About this document

After this introduction, the document is structured as following:

- ✚ **Chapter 1** contains a **general description of the opportunities and challenges related to PVI introduction** and a brief description of a EAFRD FI with the potential to facilitate the market uptake of the technology.
- ✚ **Chapter 2** presents the **framework of EAFRD FIs** and the preliminary work that must be carried out by the MAs before starting to work on the **ex-ante assessment** of a PVI tailored EAFRD FI.
- ✚ **Chapter 3** is focused on the **market analysis** that justifies the use of an FI to support PVI projects and in the estimation of the added value which is expected to deliver.
- ✚ **Chapter 4** deals with the determination of the **capacity of the EAFRD FI to attract additional funds to PVI projects** and with the analysis of relevant previous experiences of EAFRD FIs.
- ✚ **Chapter 5** describes the proposed **investment strategy** for the FI and presents details regarding its operative and governance structure.
- ✚ **Chapter 6** proposes how to stablish and quantify the **expected results of the FI**, related monitoring and reporting procedures and conditions and timing when updating the FI if needed.
- ✚ **Annex 1** presents a **methodology** to estimate the quantitative aspects of the FI, including its size, impact, leverage capacity and cost of the FI for the RDP.
- ✚ **Annex 2** is a **case study** exemplifying the application of the methodology presented in Annex 1 to produce an ex-ante assessment of the FI.

1. Opportunities and challenges for the decarbonization of European irrigated agriculture

Irrigated agriculture is key for Europe as it is responsible for more than 40% of the continent total food production. Ensuring a sustainable model for irrigation is particularly relevant considering EU's environmental and geopolitical challenges. As their main inputs, water and energy consumption are the most relevant sustainability issues related to irrigated agriculture. In this regard, in EU's Mediterranean countries, more than 70% of all freshwater withdrawals are related to irrigation, causing stress on existing natural resources (Wriedt et al. 2009). This huge quantity of water must be pumped from wells, rivers and reservoirs to the crops, a process that requires intense energy consumption. Furthermore, a much-needed sustainable water model for European irrigation will need additional pumping power to expand precision agriculture techniques and desalinization. Such techniques require pressurization, which is costly in terms of energy. Thus, many CAP objectives are in conflict with the existing energy model of irrigation which rely on fossil fuels and is a major producer of greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions⁴. Therefore, the promotion of an energy model for irrigation capable of delivering large amounts of energy from clean sources and at affordable cost must be considered within the RDPs of regions with irrigated land. Such energy model is technically possible due to the availability of specifically designed for irrigation green energy technologies based on PVI.

1.1 PVI: a key ingredient for the green transition in the irrigated agriculture

PVI consists of the integration of a photovoltaic system into an irrigation infrastructure in order to reduce or avoid the need of using conventional energy sources to transport and pressurize water. Due to the specific requirements of irrigation infrastructures and practices, PVI requires the use of highly specialized technical solutions and operation and maintenance practices. Therefore, upgrading a new or existing irrigated infrastructure to PVI require high up-front investments and long payback times, limiting its suitability to those farmers with access to long-

⁴ European Union's irrigation consume more than 24 TWh which causes GHG emissions of more than 4 million tons of CO₂

term, low-cost sources of finance. This factor is the most important barrier to PVI dissemination and, consequently, to the decarbonization of irrigated agriculture.

In order to overcome the aforementioned barrier, tailored financial instruments and business models with the capacity to attract affordable capital to PVI projects can be supported by the RDPs. In this regard, business models based on power purchase agreements (PPA) have proven their capacity to facilitate investments in clean technologies in many contexts (Drury et al. 2012). PPAs provide long-term guarantees for investors and consumers of clean energy, a requisite to make projects investable and to facilitate access to affordable finance. A PPA consists in a bilateral agreement between an energy consumer (such as an irrigator) and a specialized provider of clean energy, as shown in Figure 1. A PPA typically establishes the price of the energy for the consumer, the amount of energy to be delivered to the consumer and the length of the agreement between the parties. Once these details are agreed, the provider executes the required investments and carries out the necessary activities to operate and maintain the systems in optimal conditions. Then, the consumer pays a periodic bill for the energy and receives a guarantee of service from the provider during the life of the PPA. For the PPA model to be viable, it is required that competitive energy prices can be offered to consumers, equal or lower than the price of incumbent alternatives. In this regard, the capacity of the PPA provider to offer such competitive prices to potential consumers depends on accessing to long-term affordable funds to pay for the necessary upfront investments.

Figure 1. PPAs allow energy consumers to switch to clean sources without having to pay high up-front costs and without assuming building and operating risks and complexities. The model has proven effective to facilitate the market up-take of clean energy solutions in many contexts. Nevertheless, the viability of the PPA business model depends on access to low-cost, long-term finance to be competitive with incumbent energy solutions.

1.2 An EAFRD FI tailored to facilitate PVI market uptake

The PPA business model depends on the availability of long-term, low-cost finance for the projects. As a result, the market of PPAs is dominated by a few large companies with direct access to capital markets. In general, such developers are focused in large projects oriented to commercialize electricity through the public electricity grid, with much less activity in self-consumption solutions such as PVI. The PVI market is best suited to more granular actors, such as local SMEs with technical expertise and commercial networks in the irrigation sector. Nevertheless, such type of companies relies on their own resources or on loans from commercial banks to obtain funds for their operations. These sources of funding are not adequate in terms of cost and maturity to fund PPAs, unless a high level of guarantees is provided to the lenders by the promoters. As banks have limited or none experience assessing the risk of PPA-PVI, additional guarantees to those of the projects are normally required to be provided by the promoters. Nevertheless, most SMEs prefer to use their existing guarantees to back operations with shorter maturity than PVI-PPA, so the PVI-PPA market remains underdeveloped. In the current scenario of increasing rates of interest, financial gap causing the described situation is expected to worsen.

The described situation is a classic case of market imperfection leading to suboptimal investment in PVI projects. In order to overcome this situation, the use of FIs is particularly effective, as they can be designed to specifically address the market failure that is hampering a match between investors and projects (Dhruba 2018). That is precisely the objective of EAFRD FIs, that have been included in the RDPs as a tool to complement existing supporting measures such as grants and subsidies in order to fulfil the objectives of CAP⁵. In the context of PVI, and specially of large-scale PVI, it is particularly relevant to support the creation of a network of specialized providers of PPAs by allowing local SMEs and investors to participate in the development of the market. In order to achieve this objective, an EAFRD FI can provide additional guarantees to lenders, facilitating PPA providers access to bank finance with the necessary characteristics in terms of cost, leverage and term. This document contains a description of such an FI, which will transfer the riskiness of loans to PVI projects from banks to a fund established with resources of the RDP and other co-investors. The reduction in the riskiness

⁵ A comprehensive description of EAFRD FIs can be found at [“EAFRD financial instruments in 2014-2020 Rural Development Programmes”](#)

of the loans will result in reductions in the cost of capital of PVI projects and, consequently, in the cost of the clean energy that irrigators need.

The proposed FI will be available to projects on condition of compliance with a specific set of technical and economic characteristics in order to ensure reliability and suitability to the needs of irrigators. In order to ensure the effectiveness of the FI, a number of complementary actions can be carried out, including facilitating technical support to irrigators, promoters and financial intermediaries. As a result, irrigators will have improved access to clean energy solutions at competitive prices and with guarantees of performance.

In any case, the introduction of the proposed EAFRD FI within the RDPs requires a number of actions that must be carried out by the MA in order to demonstrate its coherence with the objectives and measures of the RDP and the related regulations and funding programmes. The design, funding and implementation of EAFRD FI is detailed in the CPR and involves a variety of stakeholders to work in coordination over time, so a careful planification is required.

The proposed EAFRD financial instrument will take the form of a guarantee to support lending to on-farm investment. In this regard a number of financial instruments of this sort have been implemented and documented so they can be used as a reference for the proposed one⁶. In the following sections a chronological description of the actions is provided as well as relevant aspects that must be taken into consideration before, during and after the implementation of a EAFRD FI dedicated to PVI.

⁶ Detailed information is available regarding the design and execution of EAFRD in the form of guarantees including [Nouvelle-Aquitaine](#), [Portugal](#), [Poland](#), [Greece](#) and [Romania](#).

2. Preliminary work

FIs are more effective when they are designed to address the needs of a specific asset class. This is because the risks, that ultimately the FI aims to price and to relocate, are determined, to a great extent, by factors at the asset level, including the technology, the business model and the specific regulatory framework among others. For example, a FI designed to provide a specific level of guarantees to investments in farms of any type will have less impact than a FI designed to specific projects such as, for example, “loans to young farmers buying land in the dairy sector”. Similarly, an EAFRD FI for PVI is expected to have more impact if it is oriented to a specific business model and segment of the market. In particular, **the FI proposed here is designed to support medium to large scale PVI systems, ranging from a few hundred KW to several MW**. These systems are adequate to supply clean energy to large irrigation infrastructures with high energy demands. To build and operate such type of systems requires specialized know how and high investments so the advantages of the PPA model are particularly relevant. Thus, in order to assess the suitability of the FI, the MA must consider to what extent the type of irrigation infrastructure that exists or is envisaged in its territory is suited to medium to large PVI systems. If the needs of the irrigators are best satisfied with small PVI (< 100 kWp), then it is likely that different types of support are more adequate, including grants and subsidies.

Alongside the definition of the systems, the other key element of the proposed FI is that it is designed to support PVI projects under the PPA business models. Among the different reasons of focusing in such business model, the need of introducing sound and reliable quality standards is particularly relevant. In contrast with business models based on the direct ownership of the PVI systems by the irrigators, PPA introduces a clear incentive in PVI suppliers to design, build and operate high quality systems, a key aspect to ensure the results of the investment in the long term. Thus, before considering the implementation of the proposed FI, the MA must confirm that the regulatory framework is compatible with the PPA business model. In particular the legislation must allow that the ownership of a self-consumption energy systems could be different than the consumers themselves. If these preconditions are met, the MA may consider to further explore the inclusion of an EAFRD FI within the RDP by conducting an “ex-ante appraisal” described below.

2.1 Ex-ante appraisal of the ‘rationale for the use of financial instruments financed by the EAFRD’.

The FI can be introduced in the RDP during its initial redaction at the beginning of the programming period or in a revision. In both cases, the CPR indicates the need of producing an ex-ante assessment in order to establish the different details of the FI. In order to avoid a waste of resources in producing ex-ante assessments of fundamentally flawed FIs, **an ex-ante appraisal must be carried out in advance**. The ex-ante appraisal provides a general justification of the FI, and must provide evidence of the consistency of the FI with the intervention logic of the RDP, with its financial tools and with the governance structures in place.

Consistency with the intervention logic

The **FI must contribute to the relevant focus areas and measure objectives already defined in the RDP** as well as to the specific objectives it would like to strengthen in line with Article 58 of Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 (CPR). Furthermore, the FI indicators must be consistent with priorities, focus area and measure related to it. For this reason, the **MA must identify if the RDP includes specific measures to support the modernization of irrigation** or any other category that can contain the new FI.

Consistency in financial terms

The **MA must identify the measure or measures that will fund the FI in coherence with the RDP strategy and priorities**. Also, any other supporting instruments susceptible of being used for supporting PVI must be identified. In the case of the proposed FI, the relevance of large-scale irrigation in the area must be assessed in order to identify the potential impact. Also, it must be established the relevant conditions of the credit market for PVI projects, for example by consulting with local banks the expected requirements for a loan to produce a typical large scale PVI. The planned introduction of a technical support scheme to irrigators, SMEs and financial intermediaries can also be included in this part⁷.

⁷ Grants for technical support, which are combined with an FI in a single operation are provided for the preparation of the prospective investment (Article 37(7), (9) of the CPR and Article 5 Regulation 480/2014).

Consistency of the FI with governance structures

The **proposed FI must be consistent with the existing governance structures of the RDP**. In particular, the MAs of regional RDPs must ensure that the FI is consistent with existing national FIs if they are available and/or with other programs such as the European Structural and Investments Funds (ESIF).

3. Market assessment and added value

The results of the ex-ante appraisal may indicate the existence of a financial gap for PVI projects and the opportunity of introducing an EAFRD FI to overcome the situation. In that case, **a complete ex-ante assessment must be produced and presented to the EAFRD authorities for their approval**⁸. The ex-ante assessment must present detailed evidence regarding the existence of a specific market failure and/or a suboptimal investment situation which is relevant for the irrigation sector to carry out PVI projects⁹. The CPR indicates the methodologies that must be used to carry out the related market analysis. The following sections have been produced in order to facilitate the identification and quantification of the elements that can lead PVI investments to such situation in a specific region in accordance with the relevant regulation and methodologies of the EAFRD.

3.1 Market assessment

The **first element to be established in the ex-ante assessment is the existence of a market failure** that can be overcome or at least mitigated by an FI. For this, the EAFRD regulation establishes four aspects that must be considered including:

- 1) The economic context of the irrigation sector and of the providers of PPA-PVI to irrigators.
- 2) The supply side of finance for PVI.
- 3) The demand side of finance for PVI.
- 4) The existing gap between supply and demand of finance for PVI and the factors causing it.

⁸ A repertoire with the ex-ante assessments of the financial instruments presented to the EAFRD can be found at [FI-Compass](https://www.ficompass.eu/sites/default/files/publications/EVALUACION_INSTRUMENTOS_FINANCIEROS.pdf). In particular, the ex-ante assessment of the FI where the proposed FI is intended to be integrated in the case of Spain can be found at: https://www.ficompass.eu/sites/default/files/publications/EVALUACION_INSTRUMENTOS_FINANCIEROS.pdf

⁹ A general analysis of the financing needs of the agriculture sector can be found at: <https://www.ficompass.eu/eafrd/fi-compass-study-financial-needs-agriculture-and-agri-food-sectors-24-eu-member-states>.

3.1.1 Economic context of irrigation

This part must present **a description of the irrigation sector in the region in quantitative and qualitative terms**. It must also introduce the technological and economic challenges related to the decarbonization of the sector and the relevance of PVI and the PPA business model to improve the existing situation. In order to illustrate such aspects, the ex-ante assessment can include information related to the following aspects:

- Type of irrigators, organization and size of the sector, production and trends.
- Economic performance of the different stakeholders and subsectors.
- Incumbent energy options for irrigators, costs and alternatives.
- Impact of related problems of existing energy model: evolution of the price of the energy, volatility and environmental impact.
- The potential of PVI, description of the technology¹⁰ (Solaqua Project 2021a).
- Barriers to adoption of PVI: upfront cost, uncertainty over the results, high LCOE.
- Business models: Availability of TPO, PPAs, surplus commercialization, risk relocation, potential of local SMEs and investors to provide tailored business models and finance.

3.1.2 Analyzing the supply side of PVI funding

PPA is a type of TPO business models where the PVIs are not directly owned by the farmers that consume the energy produced by them (Davidson, Steinberg, Margolis 2015). Instead, the PVIs are owned, operated and maintained by specialized entities know as Special Purpose Vehicles (SPVs). SPVs are investment vehicles frequently used in infrastructure investments, including renewable energy, due to the advantages that presents to promoters. By allocating all the assets liabilities related to a specific project or set of projects into an SPV, promoters can optimize the financial structure and control their exposure to the risks while investors can better assess the operation and isolate it from the financial situation of the promoter. On this regard, SPVs are the energy industry standard for renewable projects, so they must be considered the final recipients of the FI. Nevertheless, the beneficiaries of the FI will be the irrigators, as they will have access to affordable, reliable PVI that will not be available otherwise in competitive terms.

¹⁰ A detailed description of the technology including the necessary quality standards in EPC and O&M can be found at "[Best Practices for Photovoltaic Irrigation](#)".

A specific protocol will be included in order to ensure that all the operations supported by the FI result in benefits for the irrigators.

As the FI is intended to support PPAs, **the analysis of the funding available in the market for PVI projects must be focused on the availability of funds for SPVs established to own and manage PVI-PPA**. A suitable information to assess such issue can be obtained from the sector of energy service companies (ESCOs) which are enterprises specialized in providing energy solutions to their customers on the basis of designing, implementing and monetizing energy efficiency and self-consumption projects. Thus, in order to complete this part of the ex-ante assessment, the MAs are advised to verify if local ESCOs are already offering PPA to PVI, the average conditions in terms of cost, guarantees and length and the technical quality of the related projects. If such product is not already available, a number of quotations can be demanded for a typical PVI project, with the technical specifications described in [“Standardized power purchase agreement for photovoltaic irrigation”](#) (Solaqua Project 2021).

Identifying financial providers and financial products

In order to carry out their activities ESCOs, or any other entity offering PPAs, rely on long term finance, normally as **a combination of equity and debt**. Equity investors in TPO projects include companies of the energy and infrastructure sectors and specialized investment funds which are used to participate in capital intense projects with long paybacks. Equity investors provide finance and often technical expertise to the projects and demand a return consistent with the riskiness of the investment and the overall market conditions. The level of return demanded by equity providers is the cost of equity of related PVI projects. For the purposes of the ex-ante assessment, the **fair rate of return (FRR) of equity providers of PVI-PPA can be estimated**¹¹.

Equity finance for TPO projects is often complemented with debt, normally provided by commercial banks. On the basis of the business plan and the guarantees available, banks assess the riskiness of the projects in order to determine its capacity to produce sufficient cash flows to repay the debt as well as the creditworthiness of the borrower. Banks can accept the PPAs as

¹¹ The FRR is applied in several decisions of DG Competition. It is understood as a risk adjusted rate of return that is comparable with other opportunities in the market segment for the type of investment. It is determined by the risk profile of the investment. The managing authority has to assess what could be considered as FRR according to market data. Where no market data are available or the market is very limited, the FRR could be determined by an independent expert through analysis of industrial benchmarks and market risk.

guarantees (collateral) of the loan so the entity promoting the PVI can reduce or eliminate the use of its own guarantees in a specific project, facilitating the expansion of its activities.

Alongside private funds, PPA-PVI projects may be eligible to obtain finance from public sources such as grants or subsidies as well as other type of support such as technical assistance. The ex-ante assessment must also include a description of such funds and assistance, including those of the RDP and those from any other program.

Thus, in order to produce this part of the ex-ante assessment, the MAs must identify 1) the suppliers of PPAs for PVI in particular ESCOs, 2) the suppliers of equity for PPAs and/or for ESCOs and 3) the suppliers of debt for PPAs and/or for ESCOs with special attention to commercial banks and 4) the availability of public funds to finance ESCOs or similar activities. Once the providers and types of financial products for PPA-PVI are identified, the ex-ante assessment must quantify its size and the details of the conditions such as cost, guarantees and maturity.

Quantifying the funding available to PVI

European equity investors in energy-related projects control large pools of capital, meaning that if the projects meet the adequate requisites, funds will be available. Nevertheless, equity capital is relatively expensive, ranging from 8% to 15% FRR, so it must be leveraged with cheaper sources of finance, such as debt and public funding, in order to reduce the cost of PVI-PPAs to levels competitive with incumbent energy solutions. Furthermore, equity investors demand a minimum size of the projects in order to consider them investable and to dilute the fixed costs of investment appraisal and management. That means that a high level of standardization must be present in the PPA-PVI so many projects can be easily bundle into pools of sufficient size¹² (Solaqua Project 2021b).

As the requisites of equity investors in terms of risk and return are quite rigid and uniform and the price of the PPAs for the irrigators must remain competitive, it is mainly the availability of accessing to suitable debt what determines if any given project is financially viable. In the case of PVI-PPA such debt must allow to offer energy prices to irrigators no higher than incumbent alternatives. For example, in the case of Spain, this means that debt for PVI-PPA projects must have a cost below 3%, a maturity of at least 20 years and provide funding amounting at least

¹² A detailed description of the use of PPA-PVI as collateral for financial instruments can be found at [“PV-irrigation financial instrument for institutional investors”](#).

75% of the required investment with the guarantee of the PPAs. Otherwise, it will be not possible to meet the return demanded by equity providers (around 10%) while offering competitive prices of the energy for irrigators (60 € MWh or less).

As a result of the impact of the cost of debt in the price of the energy, the quantification of the funding available for PVI must be focused in the prevailing conditions of the credit market for ESCOs/TPOs. This task can be carried out by contacting with several banks and asking for loan offers providing business plans compatible with competitive prices of energy for irrigators. Furthermore, research can be conducted to establish the prevailing credit conditions for TPO operators such as ESCOs. On that basis, the ex-ante assessment must present evidence of the credit conditions available for PVI-PPA and estimate the resulting LCOE of PVI¹³.

3.1.3 Analyzing the demand side of PVI funding

Once the supply side of PPA-PVI is established, it is required to identify the demand side of finance for PVI under TPO models, ie, the interest of irrigators in the solution. Thus, the ex-ante assessment must present an estimation of the potential demand of PPA-PVI among irrigators, both at current conditions and in the case that the FI is introduced (and allows competitive prices of PVI). To establish such figure, alongside the use of the methodology indicated by the EAFRD managing authority (EC/EIB 2016) a survey can be carried out and/or existing literature can be consulted (Pombo-Romero 2022). By comparing the demand of PVI-PPA at prices consistent with existing credit conditions, the specific risk of PVI-PPA and the type of finance that would facilitate PVI-PPA prices to be competitive with incumbent alternatives, it would be possible to identify the met and unmet demand of credit for PVI. The quantitative calculation can be carried out using the methodology presented in Annex 1.

3.1.4 Analyzing the gap between supply and demand

A general analysis of the financing gap of the agriculture sector in Europe can have been carried out by the European Commission ([EC/EIB, 2020](#)) which can serve as a starting point to identify the specific needs of the irrigation sector. Nevertheless, the proposed financial instrument is tailored to PVI so the analysis must focus on the availability of long term, low cost finance for

¹³ A tailored assessment methodology of the cost of PVI can be found at Solaqua's "[Economic assessment methodology for PV irrigation](#)".

PVI projects and in the impact of the credit conditions at LCOE level. In case that the resulting LCOE of PVI in the existing credit conditions is higher than the cost of existing energy alternatives for irrigators, it can be assumed the existence of a gap between demand and supply of finance for PVI-PPA. This validates the relevance of introducing an EAFRD FI in the RDP to close the gap. Then, the ex-ante assessment must analyse such gap in order to establish if it is a result of a market failure or it is caused because PVI-PPA projects are inherently non-viable financially. If the analysis indicates that the PVI-PPA LCOE calculated using lowest possible cost of debt and the largest possible debt leverage (and a reasonable subsidy on CAPEX) is still much higher than the cost of incumbent energy alternatives, then it can be concluded that the financial gap is not mainly caused by a market failure, so an EAFRD FI is not relevant. In particular, it is necessary to establish the default probability of PVI systems in relation to incumbent alternatives¹⁴. If that is not the case and a significant reduction of price of PVI-PPA is achievable by, then the MA can conclude that a market failure is the main cause of the financial gap. At this point, the market analysis has to explore the reasons of the market failure.

In order to analyse what is causing the observed market gap of PVI-PPA finance, information must be obtained from debt providers (banks) in relation to the factors that affect the conditions of loans. In the case of PPA-PVI, a market failure causing suboptimal availability of credit can be caused by a variety of reasons that prevents banks from lending to such projects including lack of credit history of the SPVs, insufficient collateral, lack of knowledge of the technology and its risks, excessive maturity of the projects or specific banking policies among others. A survey can be conducted targeting banks, in order to identify the relevant factors and to assess their impact in terms of finance availability, cost, term and leverage.

3.2 Added Value

At this point the MA has justified the opportunity of introducing an EAFRD FI in the form of guarantees to remedy a market failure that is a barrier to the introduction of PVI. Now the MA must estimate the added value that such FI is expected to deliver, in particular, in comparison with other supporting tools such as grants. The related part of the ex-ante assessment contains

¹⁴ The calculation of the default probability of PPA-PVI can be carried out by assuming that it is equivalent to the irrigator owning a call option over the cost of the energy expected to be consumed during the lifespan of the contract. If the value of such option falls below the cost of early termination of the PPA then the project can be considered in default.

four different sections in order to provide 1) quantitative and 2) qualitative estimation of the added value of the FI, 3) to assess the consistency with other forms of public support to PVI and 4) to identify possible State aid implications.

3.2.1 Estimating the quantitative value added of a PVI FI

The main quantitative contributions in terms of added value of EAFRD FIs are related to their revolving nature and to their capacity to attract or “lever” additional public and private capital to targeted investments. The proposed FI is aimed to “unlock” the access of SPVs to debt suited to PVI-PPA projects, a necessary step to involve equity investors. As mentioned, the level of guarantee delivered by the FI must be sufficient to reduce the LCOE of PVI to the price of energy currently paid by irrigators. The ex-ante assessment must **identify what level of guarantees are demanded by the banks to offer debt in the conditions of interest rate, term and leverage compatible with the targeted LCOE, the FRR and the CAPEX and OPEX of PVI**. The calculations can be carried out using the methodology presented in Annex 1. The results will allow to estimate the quantitative added value of the FI following the three proposed methodologies of the EAFRD regulation including the multiplier ratio, the leverage effect and the revolving effect (EC/EIB 2016)

3.2.2 Estimating the qualitative value added of the FI

Alongside added value in terms of triggered investments in PVI projects, the proposed FI can have also **positive impacts in other aspects that must be explored and estimated in the ex-ante assessment**. Among the different qualitative value added that can be analysed the following ones are particularly relevant:

- **Address the market gap while minimising market distortion.** Supporting PVI projects with grants to irrigators have the undesired effect of deter viable projects until a grant is secured. This tends to happen even if the project has a positive return in absence of the grant, as obtaining the grant itself become a relevant factor in the decision process of the irrigators. Instead, with the proposed FI the decision process of the farmers will be exclusively based on the cost of the energy offered by PVI-PPA providers.

- **Introduce quality standards and consumer protection.** The proposed FI is intended to support TPO business models in the PVI market. TPO providers have clear incentives to design, build and operate PVI systems closely matching the real needs of irrigators and with sufficient quality to deliver over its entire lifespan. In contrast, traditional providers of directly owned PVI have not such incentives, as the risks of ill-design or low reliability are mainly beard by the irrigator itself. The introduction of technical support for irrigators can guarantee that the PVI-PPA offered is suited to their specific needs and complies with the quality standards.
- **Facilitate local SMEs to be part of the PPA-PVI market.** The irrigator sector is supplied by a network of local SMEs specialized in the different tasks and technologies involved including water and energy infrastructures, agronomics, machinery and engineering solutions. Many of those SMEs are commercially and technically well placed to participate in the development of a decarbonized irrigation sector, that would become a multibillion business opportunity. Nevertheless, the SMEs seldom have access to suitable finance to participate in TPO business models, so only large companies and investment funds are operating in that sector. The proposed FI will unlock suitable funding for the operation of local SMEs in similar terms of large companies, levelling the playfield and increasing the positive impact in local communities. Technical support can be included in the FI to support SMEs in adopting best practices and quality standards in PVI-PPA production.
- **Facilitate PVI projects access to capital markets.** The proposed FI is intended to support the introduction of PVI on the basis of standardized PPAs. If a sufficient amount of standardized PVI-PPAs is available, they can be used as collateral to produce capital market oriented financial instruments such as green bonds. That would expand the base of potential investors in PVI projects by many orders of magnitude, leading to more capital available and further reductions in the cost of capital of the projects and the clean energy for the irrigators.
- **Reduce aid's management cost and time.** The administrative and management tasks related to the proposed FI will be mostly carried out by the banks acting as financial intermediaries on the basis of the EAFRD regulation. The MA will entrust implementation tasks to these banks that will be responsible for promoting the FI to financial recipients (the SPVs), monitors the FI and reports to the MAs. In contrast, a supporting measure based on grants will require the MA to directly evaluate and monitor a large number of individual applications.

3.2.3 Assessing consistency of other forms of public intervention addressing the same market

In this part of the ex-ante assessment, the MA must determine the consistency of the proposed FI with existing supporting mechanisms and tools of public intervention that can also be used to support PVI. The MA must determine **if the FI can work in a complementary manner with existing tools.**

3.2.4 State aid implications

Managing authorities should identify when and under what conditions a FI falls under State aid and when it needs to be notified to the Commission.

4. Additional Resources and previous experiences

The ex-ante assessment the MA must present evidence that the proposed **FI can attract private co-investment and additional funding for PVI projects**. In order to provide such evidence, the document should include information regarding the public and private resources to be potentially raised by the FI, the estimated leverage achieved by the FI and the need for and extent of preferential remuneration for private investors. Also, any new FI must be designed including any relevant experience and lesson learnt as a result of previous implementations of EAFRD FI. In this Chapter 4 these elements will be consider in the framework of the proposed FI for PVI.

4.1 Additional resources to finance PVI-PPA

4.1.2 Potential sources of co-invest in PVI-PPA

As a result of the analysis of the supply side of the market of PVI-PPA, a number of private and public sources of finance for PVI have been identified, including public programs, investment funds, infrastructure companies and ESCOs. In this part of the ex-ante assessment, a more **detailed description of such sources** must be provided, considering the specific context of the proposed FI (guarantees for loans to SPVs). As the final recipients of the proposed FI is very specific, the potential sources of co-invest can be easily identified on the basis of a simulated project. In order to carry out this task it is advised to work alongside entities already operating in the sector such as ESCOs, dedicated funds (public and private), energy agencies and banks in order to produce a mock SPV offering PVI-PPAs based on the standards, business projects and simulation tools developed by the project SolaQua. In this regard, it is relevant to consider also a scenario including the securitization of the PPAs, as it would result in a significant increase of the potential sources of co-invest.

4.1.2 Expected leverage of the FI

The proposed EAFRD FI has the capacity to attract additional resources to PVI investments by unlocking banking finance and equity finance in sequence. Nevertheless, the ex-ante assessment

must produce a **quantitative estimation of the leverage** of the FI without considering the final recipients. In order to produce such estimation, the MA can follow the methodology presented in Annex 1.

4.1.3 Preferential remuneration for private investors

In order to produce the required effects, the FI must include a preferential remuneration scheme for the banks in the form of a first loss. This is an exception to the State aid regulations that assume, as the standard approach, that private and public investors share exactly the same risks and rewards. As a result, the ex-ante assessment must provide **justification of the demanded exception and an assessment of the size of the first loss**. To comply with this requisite, the MAs can indicate the impossibility of reducing the interest rate of the loans without reducing the exposure of the banks to the risk of the PVI-PPA projects. The details of the preferential remuneration can be estimated using the methodology presented in Annex 1.

4.2 Previous experiences and lessons learnt

EAFRD FIs are a relatively new and innovative tools designed to support the execution of RDPs in the specific case of the existence of market failures. In this regard, a relevant number of experiences have been carried out by MAs all over the EU in different contexts and forms over the last years. Those experiences provide a valuable source of information in order to design, implement and execute new FIs, so the ex-ante assessment must include a section dedicated to **identify and analyse relevant past and ongoing EAFRD FIs and to describe how the lessons learnt will be applied to the new FI**. In this regard the European Commission has established FI-Compass¹⁵, a comprehensive programme to provide training and information to MAs on the use of FIs. Among other resources, **FI-Compass produces freely available reports on case studies of EAFRD FI implementation** that must be consulted when preparing this section of the ex-ante assessment.

¹⁵ <https://www.fi-compass.eu/>

4.2.1 Relevant previous experiences on EAFRD FIs

The **proposed FI has the form of a guarantee to improve access to loans for PVI projects**. Such FIs have been introduced in several RDPs to support different kind of investments and even operational expenses of farms. The MAs are advised to focus on those previous experiences of FIs consisting in guarantees to support banking credit for investment in fixed assets.

4.2.2 Success factors and pitfalls from past experience

Once the relevant experiences have been identified, the ex-ante assessment must **analyse the key success factors and pitfalls at each step of the FI life cycle**. In the case of guarantees to bank loans, limited success of the FIs has been related with the difficult of banks to assess the riskiness of the investments, shorter than needed repayment times, insufficient level of guarantees apported by the FI and limited coordination between MAs and financial intermediaries. In general, the accumulated experience indicates the convenience of designing FI tailored to specific market needs rather than using one-size fits all approaches.

4.2.3 Application of lessons learnt to the new FI (SWOT analysis)

New FIs must be designed taking into consideration the accumulated experience of the EAFRD program. The application of the lessons learnt to the new FI must be formally presented in the ex-ante assessment in a **Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis**. Also, a SWOT analysis of the FI must also be included in the ex-ante evaluation of the CAP strategic plan providing general information about its operation. Although the specific local conditions must be also reflected in the SWOTs, a number of elements are likely to be common to any region interested in the PVI FI, including the following ones:

Strengths

Size and maturity of the average PVI project. One of the factors that limited the success of previous FIs has been an insufficient size and or intensity in the use of debt of the average project. In this regard, the impact of the FI in absolute terms depends on the size of the supported projects and on the additional leverage and maturity of the finance obtained. If those variables are relatively small, the impact of the FI will be also small, reducing its attractiveness

for potential beneficiaries. In contrast, PVI projects require relatively high investments, leverages and length of the loans so the impact of the FI will be high in absolute terms.

Existence of a demand for PVI-PPA. Another factor that has been reported relevant to the success of the FIs is the existence of a sufficient demand for the eligible investments. In the case of PVI-PPA, a significant potential demand has been identified as a result of a number of surveys and market analysis¹⁶.

Creditworthiness of the sector and reliability of the energy yield of PVI. A number of FIs have been negatively affected by a perceived high risk of the investments. Nevertheless, in the case of PVI, the medium to large scale irrigation infrastructures such as the ones suited to the proposed FI, are largely owned by cooperatives and public or semi-public entities who supply water to the irrigators of the area. Such entities have a low probability of default in their financial obligations as they are usually supported by public funds in case of necessity. Furthermore, PVI systems provide a steady amount of energy during its lifespan that is relatively easy to estimate with a low level of uncertainty. Such a combination of low credit risk and low uncertainty on the results of the investment will result in more favourable risks assessments by the financial intermediaries.

Availability of quality standards and bankable collateral. Financial intermediaries of previous FI have reported difficulties to assess the suitability of eligible projects due to a lack of track record of the assets and/or insufficient collateral. This problem is more relevant when the heterogeneity of the eligible projects and the collateral is high and there are no reliable quality standards to compare with. In order to overcome this situation, the proposed FI is related with a set of quality standards including a bankable (and suited to securitization) PPA and technical support for final beneficiaries and financial intermediaries.

Simplification of the procedures for the irrigators. Another factor that has been reported as relevant to the success of the FIs is to minimise the related administrative burden for the farmers. In this regard, the proposed FI will be applied for by the SPV instead than by the irrigator/farmer, as the loan application that will obtain the guarantee will be carried out by the SPV.

¹⁶ An estimation of the potential market for on-farm RES PPAs in Spain, Greece and Italy can be found at [“Report on analysis on survey data”](#) of RESFARM project.

Opportunities

High cost and volatility of incumbent energy solutions. Over the last years the cost of energy for irrigators has increased significantly. This has a negative impact, affecting the profitability of the sector and the financial sustainability of many farms. As a result, the competitiveness of PVI has increased in economic terms, as the cost of the resulting energy does not depend on the price of fuel or electricity. The trend is towards further increases of the price of energy so the attractiveness of PVI is expected to continue to grow.

Need to reduce GHG emissions and energy dependence on non-EU suppliers. Climate-change related action is central to EU's policy including CAP and EAFRD. Furthermore, the need to decouple strategic sectors as the agriculture from unreliable or even rogue international suppliers of energy has been recently stressed by geopolitical events. The introduction of PVI is aligned with both political objectives so the introduction of a tailored FI is particularly relevant in this situation.

Increase of the cost of debt. Debt-focused FIs are less effective if the market cost of debt is low. Nevertheless, inflationary pressures and other macroeconomic factors are pushing up interest rates from the historically low levels registered during the 2010 decade. As a result, the cost of debt is on the rise, negatively affecting the competitiveness of PVI. In such a context of high cost of debt, supporting measures focused on its reduction are expected to be particularly effective and demanded.

High demand of clean-energy assets by investors. FIs are more likely to succeed if investors are attracted to co-invest in the projects. In this regard the interest of investors in clean-energy assets such as PPA-PVI is on the rise, including specialized investment funds, utility and infrastructure companies and institutional investors.

Weaknesses

Lack of experience of banks in assessing PVI-PPA projects. Difficulties to assess the riskiness of projects have been reported as a barrier to the success of FIs. This issue is expected to be present also in the case of the proposed FI, as both PVI technology and PPA business model are relatively new solutions. It is expected that financial intermediaries will lack the experience and track-record to accurately estimate the risk of the projects a factor that, if unmitigated, led to higher cost of debt or even decline of funding.

Collateral limited to the PPAs. When lending directly to farmers or to SMEs, banks frequently demand guarantees additional to the assets to be funded. Actually, the inability of many of them to provide sufficient guarantees has been reported as factor limiting the effectiveness of FIs. In the case of the proposed FI, the collateral of the loans will be limited to the assets directly owned by the SPVs, consisting exclusively in the PPAs. This may reduce the willingness of financial intermediaries to co-invest with the FI or to offer sufficient leverage.

Beneficiaries limited to those using the PPA business model. Some FIs evaluations indicate the convenience of introducing flexibility in the type of projects and beneficiaries. This may be an issue with the proposed FI as it is designed to suit SPVs producing PVI-PPA as final recipients implying that beneficiaries must introduce PVI using the PPAs offered by such SPVs.

Threats

High cost of PVI over incumbent options. The competitiveness of PVI depends on its LCOE and on the cost of alternatives. The lower PVI's LCOE and the higher the cost of alternatives, the more competitive will be PVI. Depending on factors such as the design needs of the farms, the cost of components or the price of electricity from the grid, it can happen that the difference in the cost of PVI and incumbent alternatives is still too high to be compensated by the FI alone.

Unsupportive regulation and/or administrative procedures. PVI-PPA projects are affected by several regulatory frameworks including energy and electricity, land use, environmental protection and contractual law among others. An inadequate regulatory or administrative framework can be difficult or even impede their introduction, for example by prohibiting the installation of PV generators in agricultural land or by limiting PVI ownership to self-consumers themselves¹⁷.

Resistance/reaction of incumbent actors. Irrigators are large consumers of energy and the sector spends hundreds of millions of euros every year to pay incumbent energy providers, especially electricity companies. PVI will disrupt this business as irrigators will reduce or eliminate their dependence on existing energy sources and even commercialize electricity if they produce surpluses. As a result, it is possible that incumbent actors react against PVI introduction

¹⁷ A detailed analysis of the legal and regulatory framework related to PVI in selected EU countries can be found at Solaqua's report [“Legal analysis and best practices in PVI regulation”](#).

in order to protect their interests. This can result in commercial counter-campaigns including price reductions or in political lobbying to reduce the support to PVI.

In order to produce the SWOT analysis of the FI, the ex-ante assessment must **identify its existing and possible potentials as well as the existing and potential barriers to its implementation**. Those elements must be analysed on the basis of strengths, opportunities weaknesses and threats previously described and the FI must be designed and implemented in coherence.

Existing potentials (strengths/opportunities)

FIs have performed well when the targeted investments were particularly relevant to improve farming profitability and to meet CAP requirements. This is the case of PVI investments which can **positively impact in two of the most relevant factors both at farm and at CAP level: the cost of the energy and GHG emissions**. Furthermore, as the FI is designed to reduce the cost of debt, its attractiveness will be higher in an environment of higher interest rates, as estimated to prevail over the next years.

Existing barriers (weaknesses/ threats)

Inadequate regulation and complex administrative procedures are very effective to difficult PVI introduction, reducing the demand for the FI. This is well known by incumbent actors in the business of providing energy for irrigation so it is possible that the needed change will not have their full support. MAs and other stakeholders must take this factor into consideration in order to improve the regulatory and administrative framework and to counterbalance lobbying from incumbent actors.

Possible potentials (weaknesses/opportunities)

Difficulties in assessing the riskiness of the projects by the financial intermediaries have been often referred as a barrier to the implementation of FI. This can result in reduced access to finance for innovative projects such as PVI, as the experience of banks with such assets is limited. In order to mitigate this factor, the proposed FI is linked with a set of best practices, assessment methodologies and standards that will support the implementation of the FI by the different stakeholders, including banks themselves. For this reason, it is also relevant to combine the

guarantee with technical support to financial intermediaries, final recipients and beneficiaries, also to be included in the RDP.

Possible barriers (threats/strengths)

The demand of the FI will depend on the possibility of achieve PVI LCOE competitive with incumbent alternatives. This may or may not be achievable exclusively by the means of the FI, depending on a variety of factors that are not under the control of the MAs. In that case it will be relevant to combine the FI with other supporting measures to PVI, such as CAPEX and/or OPEX subsidies. The proposed FI is linked to a specific assessment methodology and investment strategy that facilitates the design and **implementation of complementary supporting measures**, on the basis of reducing LCOE to the required level.

5. Investment strategy

At this stage, the ex-ante assessment will include detailed information regarding the opportunity of implementing an EAFRD FI guarantee to support the market uptake of PVI on the basis of facilitating cost competitive PPAs. Based on such information, the MA must **present an investment strategy closely aligned with specific objectives under the selected priorities and focus areas, the eligibility rules under measures, the expenditure related provisions, co-financing elements and monitoring and reporting requirements as defined in the RDP**. In the case of the proposed FI, the level of detail is high as the targeted final recipients are clearly defined (SPVs) including the agricultural subsector (irrigation) and the type of investments (PPA-PVI). Furthermore, it is relevant to introduce technical requirements to the PVI systems and the PPAs in order to protect consumers and investors. These details must be reflected in the funding agreements to be subscribed with the banks acting as financial intermediaries.

5.1 Definition of the financial product

The investment strategy section of the ex-ante assessment must **contain a justified selection of the most appropriate financial product**. In this case, **the financial product is a guarantee for portfolios of loans to SPVs to fund PVI projects under the PPA business models combined with technical support for irrigators, suppliers and financial intermediaries**. The selection is justified by the high impact in PVI prices of the cost of debt, the difficult of obtaining suited finance for such projects in the prevailing credit market conditions, in particular for SMEs, and the lack of expertise and know-how regarding the technology among the different stakeholders. The ex-ante assessment must also present in this section details of the proposed FI including:

Forecasted range of interest rates: The necessary level of interest rate of the bank loans to be achieved as a result of the guarantees provided by the FI must be estimated. This can be done by adjusting the cost of debt in the LCOE formula to the level that equals LCOE to the prevailing cost of energy for irrigators, the FRR of equity investors and the CAPEX and OPEX of PVI. A methodology to assess the targeted interest rate and a case study with an example of its application is presented in Annex 1 and 2.

Collateral: The collateral of the loans to the SPVs will consist exclusively in the PPAs. For that reason, the PPAs must include a sufficient level of guarantees presented by the irrigator and enforceable mechanisms to enforce the contracts. It is advisable to use a standard both in the

PPAs and in the technical specifications of the PVI commercialization, design, construction and operation.

Term of the loans: The duration of the loans must match the duration of the PPAs and the lifespan of the systems. In most cases this means repayment periods of around 20-25 years.

Grace periods: A grace period should be included consistent with the business plan of the PVI-PPA promoters. As a general rule, a one-year grace period should be considered to allow for the first cash flows from the PPAs to be obtained by the SPVs.

Maximum eligible investments: The FI is aimed to support medium to large scale PVI projects. Some of these projects can require investments of over € 1M, and a single SPV can include several projects. As a result, the maximum eligible investment per project and per beneficiary must reflect this scale.

Risk assessment methodology. A dedicated risk assessment methodology of PVI-PPA and a technical support scheme should be included in order to support banks' to assess the projects. As the actual risks associated with the technology and the business models can be insufficient understood until a sufficient track-record is available, provisions must be included in order to record and analyze the actual performance of the assets.

Technical support for final recipients. PVI is an innovative solution that requires specialized knowledge in order to design, build and operate reliable and lasting systems suited to the needs of the irrigators and the rest of stakeholders. In this regard, there is a risk of insufficiently qualified PVI providers introducing unsuited PVI systems or flawed PPA arrangements resulting in negative outcomes for irrigators and mistrust in the technology. In order to avoid such situation, it is relevant to facilitate the development and quality of the projects supported by the FI. This can be carried out by including technical support for final recipients in the FI operation and standardized contracts suited to the needs of the different stakeholders (Solaqua project 2021). In this regard it is suggested to introduce technical support in order to produce an independent evaluation of the PVI offers received by the irrigators.

5.2 Governance structure

The ex-ante assessment must **present the envisaged governance structure for the FI under Article 38 of CPR**. Among the different options available, a suited governance structure for the proposed FI is entrusting implementation tasks to commercial banks under Article 38(4)(b). The

selected commercial banks will act as intermediaries with the final recipients, the SPVs, and will report to the MA the details of the execution. The SPVs will use the loans exclusively to produce PVI for irrigators following the PPA model and in compliance with the quality, commercial and contractual standards determined by the MA. The SPVs will use the PPAs as collateral of the loans. In case of default on a loan caused by an irrigator (breach of obligations of the PPA), the SPV will be able to activate the guarantee of the FI and the bank will receive compensation from the fund. The part of the loss corresponding to the equity investment will be directly assumed by the SPV. The described framework is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Framework of operation of the financial instrument. The FI will repay defaulted loans to the banks caused by contractual breaching of irrigators. As a result, banks will remove the riskiness of the loans leading to reduction in the cost of debt of PVI projects and resulting in affordable prices of clean energy for irrigators.

The process to select the intermediaries¹⁸ will guarantee that the commercial banks are equipped with the required tools to assess the projects. Also, the financial intermediaries will ensure that, as a result of the implementation of the FI, affordable and reliable PVI energy is available for the irrigators. In particular the selection process must guarantee that the financial intermediaries count with the following capabilities:

¹⁸ According to Article 7 of Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 480/2014.

- 1) A commercial network with relevant activity in the areas where irrigators are based and experience in the agrarian sector.
- 2) Capacity to identify the soundness of PVI-PPA projects at the different levels, including technical quality, soundness of the financial plan and creditworthiness of the SPV and the irrigator.
- 3) Ensure that the cost reductions obtained by the SPVs have an impact on irrigators. A specific indicator will be used to ensure that the expected reductions in the price of the PPAs are achieved.
- 4) Financial capacity to provide sufficient support to eligible beneficiaries in the terms and conditions suited to PVI projects.
- 5) Ability to demonstrate that, as a result of the FI, additional activity in lending to the sector of irrigation/SPVs in comparison to present activity will be achieved.
- 6) In cases where the body implementing the FI allocates its own financial resources to the FI or shares the risk, proposed measures to align interests and to mitigate possible conflicts of interest.
- 7) A reasonable level of management costs and fees for the implementation of the FI.

6. Expected results, monitoring and updating

RDPs are result-orientated tools so all their components must be coherent with the intervention logic and objectives. The EAFRD regulation also establishes that any intervention must be suited to be assessed in terms of the results of its implementation in relation to the RDP objectives. **The proposed FI is part of the RDP so it must produce tangible results that contribute to its objectives. Those results must be monitored in order to assess the adequacy of the FI and its impact.** If the monitoring reveals that the expected results are not met, the MAs must assess the underlying causes and eventually update the FI to overcome the identified problems. The ex-ante assessment must include provisions to address these issues as described in the following sections.

6.1 Expected results of the FI

The **main expected result of the proposed FI is to increase the share of irrigation production/farms/farmers powered by PVI.** In this regard, replacing the dependence on fossil-fuel of irrigated agriculture by clean, distributed PVI systems have an impact in a number of the RDP's objectives and measures, especially those regarding decarbonization and sustainability. As a result, the definition of contributions to strategic objectives and the impact indicators of the FI can be carried out as follows:

6.1.1 FI indicators

The specific impacts must be reflected in the corresponding indicators. For the case of this FI, the proposed indicators include the following ones:

- **Output indicators:** MWs of PVI funded, number of irrigators supported by the FI, total public expenditure in the FI.
- **Result indicators:** % of agriculture holdings with RDP support for investments.
- **Impact indicators:** Agricultural income, GHG avoidance¹⁹.
- **Performance indicators:** Leverage effect, management costs.

¹⁹ An environmental assessment methodology tailored for PVI projects can be found at Solaqua's ["Environmental assessment methodology for PVI"](#).

6.1.2 Contribution to strategic objectives

The EARD regulation establishes that the contribution of any FI to the RDP's strategic objectives must be identified. **In the case of a dedicated PVI-FI, a mechanism must be included in order to determine what part of the accomplishment of the strategic objectives can be attributed to it and what would have happened in the absence of the intervention.** Therefore, the ex-ante assessment must anticipate how such assessment will be carried out, including what is the relevant data that will be collected and what methodology will be used. In the case of the proposed FI, the methodology presented in Annex 1 can be used to measure the contributions to the strategic objectives.

6.3 Monitoring and reporting

The details of **the execution of FIs are to be reported to the EC within the Annual Implementation Reports.** Article 46 of the CPR indicates the information that the MA must send to the European Commission for each FI. In the case of the proposed FI, the monitoring and reporting activities will be carried out at the level of the financial intermediaries (the banks) on the basis the standard practices of the sector and in compliance with the CPR. In particular the monitoring will take place at least every three months including at least the following information:

- The amount and conditions of loans provided to SPVs.
- Details and cost of the guarantees provided by the FI.
- PVI installed capacity promoted as a result.
- Number of new irrigators and agrarian land using clean energy.
- Price of the energy offered to irrigators and terms of the PPAs.
- Estimation of the GHG avoided as a result.

6.4 Update and review

FIs' effectiveness can be affected by changes in market conditions and the general economic and political context. In the case of the proposed FI for PVI, it will be particularly sensitive to changes in energy markets and the evolution of the price of alternative sources of energy. Furthermore, relevant elements that have not been considered during the design phase can

arise at the implementation. Those unforeseen factors can reduce the suitability of the FI on its original definition and indicate the need of introduce changes to adapt to the new circumstances. In order to deal with this, Article 37(2)(g) of the CPR requires that the ex-ante assessment includes provisions for its revision and update if it no longer represents the original market conditions.

In this regard, the proposed FI include a specific assessment methodology and an effective monitoring procedure. The model presented in Annex 1 allows for the analysis of the impact in the FI of market conditions and the evolution of the price of alternative energy. Based on such model, it is possible to assess how changes in initial conditions affect the performance of the FI and what type of actions can be carried out to maximize its effectiveness. In this regard, the variables that are considered as relevant to trigger a revision process in case of deviation are the following:

- Low demand of the FI.
- Higher than expected cost of the guarantees per loan.
- Higher than expected demand of the FI.
- Inadequate details of eligibility including technical specifications, maximum size per operation, maximum number of operations per beneficiary, maximum level of guarantees and size of the first loss.
- Regulatory or policy changes substantially affecting the operation of the FI.
- Revision of the risk assessment methodology leading to substantial changes in the initial assumptions.
- Higher or lower than expected demand for the technical support scheme.

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Annex 1. Methodology to estimate the details of the FI

The FI described in this document is designed to improve access to suited capital for PVI projects by providing additional guarantees to dedicated loans. As a result, the cost of capital of the projects will be sufficiently reduced as to allow irrigators access to PVI solutions under the PPA model at competitive prices. In order to achieve this result, the FI must have the capacity to reduce the cost of debt provided by the banks while increasing the leverage and maturity of the finance. In this regard the FI will relocate the riskiness of the PVI-PPA from the SPV to the bank and, then, from the bank to the RDP. As a result, to establish the details of the FI it is needed to assess the value of the risk and the impact of the risk relocation at the level of the cost of energy for irrigators. The methodology presented in this Annex 1 has been designed to facilitate the estimation of those elements in order to produce ex-ante evaluations complying with the requirements of the CPR.

Estimating the targeted price of the energy for irrigators

The competitive price (P_C) that must achieve the PVI-PPA in order to be competitive can be assumed to be equal to the price of incumbent energy sources, such as electricity from the grid or from diesel generators. In order to increase the attractiveness of PVI, a discount of 5-10% over the incumbent energy solutions would be also desirable. In order to estimate P_C , the price of incumbent energy options must be considered over a sufficiently long period of time in order to smooth the volatility. A reasonable assumption is to obtain a sample of the price paid by the irrigators²⁰ over the last five years, including all the components of the bill, and calculate an average. Alternatively, in the case that irrigators have access to long-term fixed tariffs for their incumbent energy supply, such figure can be assumed as a proxy to P_C .

²⁰ Different typologies of irrigation/incumbent energy sources must be established as the resulting price of energy can have significant differences depending on such factors.

Calculating the levelized cost of energy of PVI

Once the targeted price P_c of the PPA has been estimated, the next step consists in **establishing the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of PVI** in the current conditions. LCOE models are often used to determine the price of the PPA, as they allow to include the impact of the time-dimension of the invested money and a measure of the riskiness of the projects into the cost of energy. LCOE methodology is particularly well suited to assess the resulting cost of energy of PVI, as it requires high upfront investments and long payback periods.

The output of an LCOE model indicates the monetary units that has been necessary to produce a unit of energy (for example €/MWh). In order to estimate the LCOE of a given project, one must divide the cost of constructing and operating an electricity generating plant by the expected total energy production, for every future period of operation. The resulting future costs and amounts of energy produced are then “discounted” using a discount rate that reflects the cost of capital of the project, as is defined in Equation 1.

$$LCOE = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{CAPEX_t + OPEX_t}{(1+WACC)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{EnYield_t}{(1+WACC)^t}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Thus, four main variables must be assessed to estimate the LCOE of a PVI project including:

1. **EnYield_t; Expected energy yield of the system in year t.** This variable depends on a number of factors including the solar irradiation in the area, the design of the PVI system and its degradation rate and, in particular, the seasonality of the irrigation needs (see SolaQua deliverable 2.10 “Best Practices for Photovoltaic Irrigation Systems”). The energy yield is normally presented in equivalent peak sun hours per year and normally fluctuates between 1,100 and 2,200.
2. **CAPEX_t; Capital expenditure.** CAPEX includes all the relevant costs that are necessary to commercialize, design, build and commission a PVI system. Among other elements CAPEX accounts for engineering activities, permits, solar modules, frequency converters, sun-trackers and civil works (see SolaQua deliverable 2.5 “Economic Assessment Methodology of PVI”). In many cases the existing irrigation infrastructure must be adapted or modernized to facilitate PVI integration including actions such as

the replacement of existing pumping units. Alongside the described costs at the beginning of the operation of PVI, CAPEX also includes planned investments to be executed after commissioning, in particular the replacement of frequency converters after 10 years of operation.

3. **OPEX_i; Operational expenditure.** PVI systems require high up-front costs that can be compensated by relatively low OPEX, as no fuel is required to produce energy. Nevertheless, in order to ensure an adequate operation and maintenance of the systems, a number of recurrent costs must be considered including regular tasks such as cleaning and supervision, monitoring, fixing any malfunction and general administration and management (see SolaQua deliverable 2.5 [“Economic Assessment Methodology of PVI”](#)). Also, a number of contingencies must be adequately hedged by insurance policies and their cost added to the OPEX.
4. **WACC; Weighted Average Cost of Capital.** Investors demand a return for their capital that is coherent with the general level of interest rates and with the riskiness of the project. Investable projects must produce a sufficient amount of cash flows to cover their OPEX and CAPEX but also to pay for investors’ return. In the case of PPA-PVIs those cash flows are produced when irrigators pay their bills over the length of the contract, which can be 20 years or more (see SolaQua deliverable 2.5 [“Economic Assessment Methodology of PVI”](#)).

In the case of WACC, which is the LCOE component targeted by the FI, three main elements must be estimated during the ex-ante assessment: 1) the cost of equity, 2) the cost of debt and 3) the proportion of equity and debt used to fund the project known as leverage. In order to calculate the cost of equity, it is necessary to estimate the FRR of investors in PVI or comparable asset classes following mainstream methodologies²¹. Equation 2 allows for the determination of WACC of an asset *i*:

$$WACC_i = L_i * (r_f + r_i) + (1 - L_i) * (FRR) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where L_i is the leverage or proportion of debt used to fund the asset, r_f is the risk-free rate, r_i is the premium interest rate demanded by the bank to compensate for the riskiness of the asset and FRR is the fair rate of return of the equity.

²¹ A comprehensive methodological handbook for economic assessment of projects can be found at https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/studies/pdf/cba_guide.pdf

Estimating the cost of debt of PVI projects

Regarding the cost of debt and the proportion of the investment that is available in form of debt for a given project, banks determine these figures by carrying out a **risk assessment of the project**. The risk assessment essentially consists in an estimation of the default risk of the borrower on the basis of models and historic records. Once the probability of default is assessed by the bank, the decision to concede the loan and details such as the demanded guarantees, the interest rate, the length and the leverage are determined on the basis of existing regulation²² and bank policies. The cost of debt is then the result of adding a risk premium estimated for the loan (usually on the basis of the distance to default of the borrower and the Value at Risk of the lender) to the baseline or risk-free interest rate of the credit market (for example the Euribor). Nevertheless, such approach fails to identify the intrinsic value of a PPA-PVI and specifically the added value derived from the reduction in the volatility of the cost of the energy. In order to introduce such critical factors a real-option valuation approach must be applied in order to identify the default point and the distance to default of the technology itself.

Estimating the Value at Risk of PVI projects

In essence, **the standard methodology used by the banks to calculate the cost of debt of the loans²³ consists in valuing the riskiness of the operation and charge a margin over it**. As higher risks will be only be assumed by the bank if the expected return is also higher, the cost of debt will reflect this basic financial principle. In order to estimate the risk, the bank gathers relevant information regarding the loan application and introduces it into probabilistic models. The output of such models are the probability and the distance to default²⁴ of the borrower, which is the risk that the bank is assuming if loan is approved. The bank will estimate the impact of the

²² The Basel committee on banking supervision (BCBS) sets the standard for international banking prudential regulation. The current set of standards developed by the committee is known as the Basel III framework.

²³ In credit operations, VaR is defined as the maximum amount of money expected to be lost over a given time horizon as a result of borrowers' defaults, at a pre-defined confidence level. For example, if the 90% one-year VAR is € 1 million, there is 90% confidence that over the next bank the portfolio of loans will not lose more than \$1 million as a result of defaults.

²⁴ Distance to Default is a central concept in Structural Credit Models where it denotes the degree to which the assets of a borrower exceed the corresponding liabilities.

operation on its overall (or a specific portfolio of loans) Value at Risk (VaR) and will take a decision on that basis.

VaR accounts for the nominal value of portfolio which is expected to be lost with a given probability over a specific period of time. VaR is also the maximum amount of money that the bank is willing to lose in a negative scenario, for example if the bank determine that the VaR is less than € 10 M with a 90% probability, it means that the new loans must have a risk-return profile that maintains that VaR unaffected. Thus, if the average default probability of a loan is 1% annual, and 90% of times is estimated to be below 3%, the bank will assume that 3% is the premium that the borrower must pay. In that regard, the premium interest rate that the bank charges to a given loan i (see equation 2) rP_i and the leverage L_i can be assumed to be a function of the default probability $P(d)$ and the VaR, as presented in equation 3:

$$L_i, rP_i = F[P(d), VaR] \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Determining the targeted cost of debt

In order to reduce the LCOE of PVI in Equation 1, the FI must reduce the cost of debt by modifying L_i and/or rP_i in Equation 2. Those values can be set within a reasonable margin²⁵ until the condition $LCOE=P_c$ is met. The resulting targeted values of L_i and rP_i can be then sat in Equation 3. It is to note that the only parameter that can be affected by the FI is VaR in Equation 3, as it will transfer the VaR from the bank to the RDP, effectively reducing its value to the effects of calculating L_i and rP_i .

Determining the leverage and size of the FI

In order to determine the leverage of the FI, **the effective cost of the guarantee must be estimated** as well as the total amount of investments triggered by the FI. The triggered investment can be assumed to be equal to CAPEX in Equation 1, as it accounts for the total investments needed to design and built the PVI, minus the cost of the FI itself. The cost of the FI can be estimated equal to the average probability of default of the loans multiplied by its outstanding value and actualized using an appropriate discount rate, as it will be the actual

²⁵ In practical terms L_i cannot be higher than 0.9 while rP_i cannot be lower than 0.

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amount that will be consumed in the RDP. Then, the total size of the FI can be estimated as a function of the targeted investments triggered and the leverage capacity of the FI.

Annex 2. Case study

The MA of an RDP is carrying out an ex-ante assessment of an EAFRD FI in order to support the introduction of PVI. The type of irrigation systems that are presented in the targeted region have been mostly build in order to pump water from a river to reservoirs in a higher place. The MA has been in contact with several representative irrigators in order to determine the competitive price of the energy P_c . After analyzing a sample of bills of the last five years, P_c has been estimated at € 70 MWh.

Also, a technical assessment has determined that the typical PVI system suited for the irrigators of the region has an average size of 1 MWp and will produce 2,000 equivalent peak sun hours annually. Then, a project with the required specifications has been presented to a number of specialized suppliers in order to obtain estimations of the cost. As a result of the market analysis, the MA has concluded that, in order to build and operate each MW of PVI it will be required to fund a CAPEX of € 1 M and an annual OPEX of € 20,000. The MA has established in the RDP the objective to promote at least 100 MW of PVI supported by the FI.

Based on those figures, the MA has contacted with a number of existing or potential PPA providers, such as ESCOs, in order to obtain quotations for a standard PPA for PVI (see SolaQua Deliverable 2.7 [“Standard PPA contracts”](#)). The average duration of the PPA has been estimated in 20 years. Based on that information and the results of analysis carried out using suited methodologies (see SolaQua deliverable 2.5 [“Economic Assessment Methodology of PVI”](#)) the MA has estimated that the FRR of PVI investors is 10% annual return.

Then, in order to stablish the market cost of debt, the MA has stablished a working group including banks suited to act as financial intermediaries. Furthermore, an assessment has been carried out using a real options valuation of the PPA from the perspective of both the irrigator and the SPV. The default point has been estimated in 1.5 years of billing. As a result, the MA concluded that the default probabilities of the asset class PPA-PVI has been estimated to average 1% annual, remaining below 3% annual with a 90% probability, which is the level of confidence used by the banks to determine VaR. The distance to default has been estimated in 5.6.²⁶

²⁶ The distance to default is derived as the difference between the current market value of assets and the default point, scaled by the volatility of the asset value.

The banks have established that for operations with SPVs exclusively guaranteed by the PPAs, the maximum leverage offered will be equivalent to 50% of the total investments. The baseline interest rate for 20-year maturities loans (risk-free rate, r_f) has been determined to be 1.5%. This information is summarized in Table 10.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Competitive price of the energy (P_c)	70	€/MWh
Average size of the systems	1	MWp
Average production time	2,000	Equivalent peak sun hours
CAPEX	1	€ M/MWp
OPEX	20,000	€/MWp year
Cost of equity (FRR)	10%	Annual return
Time of the PPA (n)	20	Years
Risk-free rate (r_f)	1.5%	Annual return
Default probability ($E(P(d))$)	1%	Expected annual defaults (average)
Value-at-risk (VaR)	3%	Maximum loss of the portfolio with a 90% confidence (annual)
Leverage (L_i)	50%	Maximum loan over total investment

Table 1: Relevant quantitative information necessary to determine the details of the FI. This data can be obtained as a result of a collaboration between MAs and specialized stakeholders including irrigators, PVI technology suppliers, ESCOs and banks.

The introduction of the values of Table 1 in the corresponding parameters of Equation 2 results in a WACC of PVI projects of 7.25%, while the LCOE resulting of introducing the inputs of Table 1 into Equation 1 results in an LCOE for PVI of € 81.27 MWh. Such an LCOE is significantly higher than the price of incumbent alternatives (P_c ; € 70 MWh) so PVI is not cost competitive in the prevailing market conditions.

Based on the aforementioned analysis, the MA has identified a gap between the cost of capital necessary to make PVI projects financially sustainable and the cost of capital available in the market. In order to estimate the size of such a financial gap, the MA sat equation 1 until LCOE was equal to P_c (€ 70 MWh). This occurs when WACC is 2.8%. The results indicated that the size

of the existing gap between supply and demand of finance for PVI is estimated to be of 4.45%, expressed in annual cost of the capital.

At this stage, the MA has identified the need of a FI with the capacity to reduce PVI's WACC by 445 basis points. In this regard, the reductions of the WACC cannot be achieved by reducing the FRR as it must be maintained at market levels (10%), otherwise investors will not be interested in co-invest in the projects²⁷. Furthermore, r_f cannot be modified by providing guarantees, as it is not reflecting the riskiness of any asset. Thus, the targeted level of WACC must be achieved by increasing the leverage L_i and/or by reducing the premium rate of interest rP_i in Equation 2. It must be noted that, as the FI here proposed is a guarantee, the maximum level of support that can be achieved is equivalent to that that verifies that $VaR=0$ and $L_i=100\%$. Nevertheless, as lenders always require borrowers to retain a certain level of exposure to the riskiness of the project, the maximum level of L_i in practical terms can be considered around 90%. In this case, one possible combination of L_i and rP_i that results in a WACC of 2.78% is $rP_i = 0$ (meaning that the RDP assumes 100% of VaR) and L_i is consistent with banks providing SPVs with loans amounting up to 85% of CAPEX. Another alternative would be to set L_i at its maximum level (90%) and to reduce the hedging of VaR to 85%²⁸.

Once the relative size of the financial gap and the details of a suited FI have been estimated, the MA must determine the financial contribution of the RDP. In order to determine the funds that must be allocated in the RDP to the FI for every € 1M of targeted investment in PVI, a simulation can be carried out on the basis of the data of Table 1 and the assumptions on the statistical properties of the default probability $P(D)$. The objective of the simulation is to estimate the expected future VaRs during the lifespan of the loans, the average defaults for every period and the present value of such figures. In this case, the simulation indicates that in order to achieve an LCOE of € 70 MWh, the RDP must allocate € 240,000 to the FI for every € 1 M of targeted investment in the FI. Those funds must be locked in the RDP at the moment of the concession of the loan in order to remove the related VaR from the bank. Nevertheless, in order to determine the actual cost of the FI, the metric that matters is not the VaR but the average default probability which is normally significantly lower. Thus, as the loan is repaid, the related VaR is reduced, unlocking funds of the RDP that can be used to support new projects with the FI. This

²⁷ In order to reduce FRR, an equity-oriented FIs could be implemented instead or in combination with the proposed guarantee.

²⁸ It is suggested to leave some exposure of the financial intermediary to the riskiness of the loan, for example by leaving at least 10% of VaR out of the protection of the FI.

is possible because of the revolving nature of EAFRD FIs, implying that unused funds can be relocated to further operations, and because the probability default use to determine VaR is higher than the expected default $E(P(d))$ most of the time. In this case, the average expected default $E(P(d))$ is 1%, and will remain below 3% 90% of times, which is the metric used to estimate VaR. As most of times the default rates of VaR will not be met, and excess funds averaging 66% is expected to be available at the end of each year for new operations. Thus, the actual total cost of the FI for the RDP for every € 1M triggered is € 80,000 (instead of the 240,000 that are temporary locked but mostly not spent), equivalent to 8% of CAPEX.

Thus, considering that the FI has a target of triggering 100 MW of PVI, and that the necessary investment is of € 1 M per installed MW, a minimum of € 8 M should be allocated to the FI. This would result in a leverage of private investments of 12.5. In this regard, it is relevant to point that to achieve a similar reduction in the LCOE of PVI by direct grants, the necessary intensity would be in the order of 30% of CAPEX, implying funds allocations of around € 30 M. Furthermore, the costs of managing the proposed FI are expected to be significantly lower than those of an equivalent grant.

As a final remark, it has to be noted that, in the present case of study, the targeted LCOE of PVI has been achieved exclusively by reductions in WACC resulting of the implementation of the debt-focused FI. Nevertheless, in many cases it is probably that reductions in the cost of debt would not be sufficient to reduce LCOE to P_c levels. In that cases MAs can consider to complement the FI with other supporting measures including grants for CAPEX, subsidies to OPEX or even an equity-focused FI. EAFRD FI regulations allows for such complementarity if needed. In this regard, the proposed methodology allows to determine such necessity on the basis of reducing LCOE to P_c levels.

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